

From Deep Fields to Wide Surveys: A Framework for AO-Aware Target Selection and Survey Design

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ABSTRACT

Adaptive-optics (AO) spectroscopic facilities on large telescopes can deliver spatially resolved spectroscopy for large samples of galaxies across cosmic time, but survey design for these facilities must account for local guide stars and expected AO correction. This work outlines a framework for AO-aware target selection and survey design based on rapid prediction of AO image-quality metrics across large numbers of guide-star asterisms and target positions. Machine-learning models trained on AO simulations estimate key metrics orders of magnitude faster than direct simulation, making catalog-scale searches for viable natural guide star asterisms and favorable sky regions practical. Combined with simplified source models and rapid S/N estimation, the framework also supports target selection based on the probability of reaching a required S/N. Together, these components enable comparisons among legacy deep fields, AO-friendly fields, and targets drawn from wide-area surveys, and inform survey planning for future AO-fed spectroscopic facilities, including GIRMOS and ELT-class instruments.

Keywords: adaptive optics, survey design, sky coverage, target selection, guide star asterisms, machine learning, integral field spectroscopy

1. INTRODUCTION

Spatially resolved spectroscopy is central to studies of galaxy evolution because it connects global observables to internal kinematics, chemical structure, and the spatial distribution of star formation and feedback [1, 2, 3]. At redshifts near the peak of cosmic star formation ($z \sim 1 - 3$), characteristic kiloparsec-scale structure subtends angular scales of order $0.1''$, smaller than the image quality typically delivered by seeing-limited observations and therefore difficult to resolve from the ground without AO [4, 5, 6, 7]. At the same time, population studies require sample sizes larger than those usually observed with AO [8, 2]. Recent and upcoming AO-fed spectroscopic facilities such as GIRMOS, HARMONI, and MOSAIC [9, 10, 11] make it increasingly feasible to combine high spatial resolution with samples large enough to study galaxy evolution statistically rather than only through studies of a few exceptional systems.

This creates a target-selection problem that differs from conventional survey design. In AO-assisted observing, targets are selected not only by their astrophysical properties, but also by the local natural guide stars (NGS), the expected AO correction at the target position, and the extent to which AO-driven flux concentration improves the measurement of interest [7]. In advanced AO modes that rely on multiple NGS and wide-field tomographic correction, NGS geometry and sky position become especially important [12, 13].

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Figure 1: High-level overview of the AO-aware survey-design framework.

AO-assisted observing therefore cannot be treated simply as a follow-up step applied after targets have already been chosen. AO performance must instead enter the survey-design process from the start. The key question is therefore not only whether a given NGS asterism can deliver good correction, but how predicted AO performance can guide the selection of targets, fields, and observing strategies across large samples. The framework outlined here (Figure 1) links four elements: rapid AO performance prediction, all-sky asterism and field selection, target-level signal-to-noise (S/N) estimation, and comparison of broader survey strategies. The goal of this work is not to present a finished end-to-end system, but to outline the logic of the framework, describe its early proof-of-concept components, and show how those components connect.

The contribution of this work is to connect steps that are often treated independently. Traditional sky-coverage estimates and earlier AO-optimized field-selection efforts [14] each address part of the problem, but not the full chain from AO prediction to catalog-scale asterism search and ultimately survey-strategy comparison. This paper connects those steps into a single survey-design workflow and shows how its main components fit together. It is therefore a framework and methodology overview rather than a detailed presentation of any one component.

2. RAPID AO PREDICTION AS AN ENABLING CAPABILITY

The central technical requirement of the framework is the ability to estimate AO performance rapidly over many NGS asterisms, field positions, and observing scenarios. Although AO simulations remain the standard tool for physically realistic performance prediction, individual simulations can take seconds to hours, making direct use impractical for the millions of evaluations needed to optimize a large survey. End-to-end tools such as OOMAO [15] typically evolve the AO-corrected PSF in time and therefore remain expensive for large parameter searches, whereas semi-analytical tools such as TIPTOP [16] estimate a long-exposure PSF in seconds when accelerated on appropriate hardware. That computational cost makes it difficult to search large stellar catalogs for favorable asterisms, map AO performance across wide sky areas, or propagate AO predictions into target-selection.

Machine-learning (ML) models offer a practical way around this bottleneck by predicting AO performance metrics directly from the guide-star asterism and observing parameters. In this work, the models are trained using semi-analytical AO simulations generated with TIPTOP, in a simulation chain anchored to end-to-end simulations carried out with OOMAO. Those simulations represent GIRMOS MOAO operated behind the Gemini North Adaptive Optics (GNAO) system [9, 17, 18]. The resulting training set therefore inherits the speed of TIPTOP while remaining tied to the OOMAO-based GNAO+GIRMOS simulation chain. Using this simulation framework, a training and validation set of 120,000 random one to three-NGS asterisms was constructed, with guide stars spanning R -band magnitudes of 8.0–18.5 and science wavelengths sampled uniformly from 0.95–2.35 μm under fixed median atmospheric conditions at zenith angle 20° . This dataset required several days of simulation time, illustrating the computational cost even before all-sky searches or target-level optimization are attempted.

Multi-layer perceptron neural network models [19] were trained to predict Strehl ratio, enclosed energy within a 100 mas aperture, denoted EE [100 mas], and full width at half maximum. Separate models were trained for one-, two-, and three-star asterisms, and for two complementary prediction tasks: estimating field-averaged AO performance and estimating position-dependent AO performance across a $120''$ field of regard. The latter is especially relevant for AO-fed multi-object instruments, where performance must be evaluated at the locations of individual science targets. The model’s input features were designed to capture the main drivers of AO

Figure 2: Predicted versus simulated EE [100 mas] for the field-averaged (left) and position-dependent (right) ML models on held-out simulations. The dashed line indicates one-to-one agreement, the dotted lines show ± 0.02 offsets, and the insets show residual distributions. The annotated RMS values give the relative prediction error.

performance, including the relative positions of the laser guide stars, NGS brightness, asterism geometry, and wavelength. A fuller description of the feature engineering and model design involved will be presented elsewhere.

Once the simulation set has been assembled, model training is inexpensive, requiring only minutes for field-averaged models and roughly an hour for the larger position-dependent models. Preliminary results indicate that, on held-out simulations, the models reproduce simulated EE [100 mas] with relative RMS residuals of 0.2% for field-averaged predictions and 0.5% for position-dependent predictions. Figure 2 compares predictions against simulations for both models, and Figure 3 shows one example of position-dependent prediction across a field of regard. Using an Apple M4 Max (10 performance CPU cores and 32 GPU cores), prediction requires about 0.4 s per million inferences when using the GPU, while CPU-only inference is about four times slower. This makes ML prediction nearly seven orders of magnitude faster than the TIPTOP simulations used to generate the training set, and TIPTOP itself is about four orders of magnitude faster than OOMAO in our setup. While this provides a substantial increase in throughput, the model is not intended to replace AO simulation in all contexts, but to provide a fast approximation accurate enough to support AO-aware field selection, target evaluation, and survey-scale comparison across large samples.

Fast AO prediction makes it practical to carry model outputs forward into asterism ranking, all-sky mapping, and target-level S/N calculations at survey scale. In that sense, it is the enabling component that connects AO simulation to the broader survey-design workflow developed in this paper. A fuller presentation of the AO prediction tools will be given in a future paper accompanying their planned public release.

3. ALL-SKY AO MAPPING AND FIELD SELECTION

Compared with traditional sky-coverage estimates, rapid AO prediction makes it possible to characterize AO performance across the sky more directly. In multi-NGS AO systems, achievable correction depends not only on guide-star’s brightness, but also on asterism geometry, particularly in MCAO and MOAO observing modes [12, 13]. Traditional sky-coverage estimates often reduce this to the fraction of sky over which a system can operate, the probability of finding suitable guide stars, or performance-threshold curves under simplified assumptions [20, 21]. Those approaches remain useful for engineering studies, *but they do not show where AO-assisted science observations are most promising*. By combining the Gaia stellar catalog [22, 23] with AO performance prediction, this work instead evaluates sky coverage from cataloged NGS asterisms and predicted performance across the sky. This provides a directly searchable map for selecting science targets with favorable AO performance.

AO sky coverage can be defined using performance-threshold maps rather than traditional scalar sky-coverage estimates (Figure 4). These maps are evaluated on a HEALPix grid [24] with coarse order 6 pixels, with area 0.84

Figure 3: Simulated (left) and predicted (right) position-dependent EE [100 mas] across a representative field of view for one held-out NGS asterism. The agreement between the two maps highlights the model’s ability to reproduce the spatial structure of AO performance across the field.

deg², representing field-scale regions comparable to extragalactic survey fields. These pixels aggregate information from a finer order 14 pixel grid used to evaluate performance on smaller scales.

We use two complementary coverage measures. The first is a field-averaged coverage map, defined by the fraction of sky over which mean performance satisfies EE [100 mas] \geq 0.30. It represents broadly usable AO correction for imaging-like applications. The second is an on-axis coverage map, defined by the fraction of sky over which central performance satisfies EE [100 mas] \geq 0.40. It represents target-centred observations that benefit from concentrating more of the light into the extraction aperture at the science location. Multi-object spectroscopy is expected to lie between these limiting cases because each target depends on the local AO performance at its own position within the field, rather than being sensitive to performance across the field or at the field centre. These maps show how predicted AO performance varies across the sky and can support target preselection and, eventually, survey design. A fuller description of the AO-sky mapping methodology, together with a public release of the maps and the tools used to construct them, will be presented elsewhere.

The same map-based approach can also be used to construct catalogs of favorable asterisms in advance. Applying a representative GIRMOS MOAO threshold on field-averaged performance, EE[100mas] \geq 0.30, yields approximately 4×10^8 asterisms across the sky accessible from Mauna Kea after removing regions with high Galactic extinction ($A_0 \geq 0.3$, where A_0 is the Gaia total Galactic extinction parameter [25], which approximates A_V). AO-aware target selection can then be reduced to cross-matching science targets against a large precomputed catalog of NGS asterisms and AO performance estimates.

All-sky maps of predicted AO performance can reveal not only isolated favorable asterisms but also extended regions where the performance is both high and relatively uniform. Such regions become natural candidates for AO-friendly fields (AOFFs), especially when survey design benefits from contiguous target selection rather than isolated pointings. Each AOFF represents one coarse sky-map pixel. In Figure 4, the red circles mark the location of 4 candidate AOFFs selected from the on-axis coverage map. In addition to high AO performance (EE [100 mas] \geq 0.40 over \geq 70% of the field), the selection requires low Galactic dust extinction ($A_0 < 0.3$), guide-star surface density below 2.0 arcmin⁻², no stars brighter than $R = 6.0$, separation from the Galactic and ecliptic planes ($|b| > 20^\circ$, $|\beta| > 15^\circ$), and a declination accessible from major observatories in both hemispheres ($-20^\circ \leq \delta \leq 15^\circ$). The selected fields are also distributed broadly in right ascension for year-round observing.

Table 1 compares the AOFFs with established deep fields, including the 3D-HST fields [26, 27], UltraVISTA-COSMOS [28], and the Euclid deep fields [29]. The AOFFs have higher coverage than every established field in both AO sky-coverage metrics. In the on-axis metric, the mean coverage across the AOFFs is 3 times that of COSMOS and 8 times that of the least favorable 3D-HST field. The AOFFs have Galactic extinction comparable to GOODS-S. Among the established deep fields, EDF-North has the highest AO sky coverage, but its high declination limits low-airmass observing from most current and planned AO-capable observatories. Even at this

Figure 4: Two complementary AO sky coverage maps for GNAO+GIRMOS. The upper panel shows field-averaged coverage for $EE [100 \text{ mas}] \geq 0.30$, and the lower panel shows on-axis coverage for $EE [100 \text{ mas}] \geq 0.40$. Extragalactic and Euclid deep fields, and the AODF from [14], are marked. Contours trace the dust-extinction cut ($A_0 = 0.3$) and red circles mark candidate AOFF locations.

Field	RA	Dec	l	b	Area [deg ²]	Σ_{NGS} [arcmin ⁻²]	A_0	AO Sky Coverage	
								Averaged	On-Axis
AODF	07:24:03	-01:27:15	218	+7	0.84	5.08	0.49	98.3%	97.5%
AOFF-A	21:02:49	+08:23:08	57	-24	0.84	1.98	0.21	95.9%	87.7%
AOFF-B	16:49:41	+02:23:17	20	+28	0.84	1.89	0.27	95.6%	86.2%
AOFF-C	05:57:11	-19:28:16	225	-20	0.84	1.52	0.19	90.2%	78.8%
AOFF-D	08:54:23	-12:38:08	240	+20	0.84	1.35	0.20	87.6%	74.5%
EDF-North	17:58:32	+66:01:03	96	+30	23.47	0.86	0.13	65.8%	50.1%
3DHST-COSMOS	10:00:31	+02:24:00	237	+42	0.03	0.43	0.06	39.2%	27.2%
UltraVISTA-COSMOS	10:00:06	+02:12:29	237	+42	1.71	0.41	0.07	35.9%	24.9%
EDF-South	04:04:57	-48:25:13	256	-47	28.73	0.43	0.10	35.8%	25.0%
3DHST-AEGIS	14:18:36	+52:39:00	96	+60	0.03	0.34	0.08	29.4%	20.2%
EDF-Fornax	03:31:44	-28:04:44	224	-55	12.75	0.32	0.09	26.4%	18.3%
SGP	00:51:26	-27:07:42	0	-90	1.00	0.39	0.17	22.3%	15.7%
3DHST-UDS	02:17:49	-05:12:02	170	-60	0.03	0.25	0.07	18.5%	13.7%
NGP	12:51:26	+27:07:42	0	+90	1.00	0.24	0.04	18.3%	12.5%
3DHST-GOODS-S	03:32:30	-27:47:19	224	-54	0.04	0.26	0.19	16.3%	11.7%
3DHST-GOODS-N	12:35:55	+62:11:51	126	+55	0.03	0.18	0.06	14.0%	9.8%

Table 1: Comparison of AO sky coverage and field properties for the AOFFs, AODF from [14], select extragalactic and Euclid deep fields, and the Galactic poles. The l and b columns give Galactic longitude and latitude. The Σ_{NGS} column gives the surface density of guide stars satisfying $8.0 < R < 18.5$, and A_0 is the average Gaia total Galactic extinction parameter across the field, which approximates A_V . The averaged and on-axis columns give GIRMOS MOAO AO sky coverage. Extragalactic deep-field values are averaged over their footprints. The Galactic-pole entries are averaged over patches centred on the poles.

stage, field selection based on predicted AO performance can identify regions substantially better suited to science observations with AO.

This remains a preliminary comparison, but the difference becomes clearer in a direct comparison between an established extragalactic field and an AOFF. Figure 5 compares the guide-star and asterism distributions in COSMOS and AOFF-A. Figure 6 compares the resulting maps of maximum predicted EE [100 mas]. AOFF-A contains a denser and more uniform distribution of asterisms that covers nearly the full field. Where usable asterisms exist, the local maximum EE [100 mas] values are broadly similar in the two fields, but most targets in AOFF-A fall in regions with scientifically useful AO correction. In practice, this means that a much larger fraction of a target catalog can be used effectively in AOFF-A than in COSMOS.

The Adaptive-Optics Deep Field (AODF) identified in [14] a relevant benchmark. It lies at lower Galactic latitude and provides near-complete AO sky coverage, but has substantially higher Galactic extinction and a much more crowded stellar field than the AOFFs. For extragalactic work, the balance may favor the AOFFs, particularly for next-generation AO systems whose improved performance can relax guide-star limitations that motivated the AODF’s selection. A fuller comparison will be the subject of future work.

At this stage, AO prediction connects directly to observational planning. AO performance is no longer evaluated only after candidate targets have been chosen, but treated as a mappable and searchable property of the sky that can guide target-list construction and field selection.

4. TARGET SELECTION AND PROBABILISTIC SURVEY DESIGN

Extragalactic surveys require long integrations, so survey design should prioritize fields and targets where AO performance improves observing efficiency for the required measurements. Fast AO prediction makes it possible to preselect targets by applying spatial-resolution-related thresholds on AO performance metrics. Spatial resolution alone, however, is not enough for survey design. Achievable S/N also determines source detectability and observing efficiency. A target may look attractive because it lies near a favorable asterism, yet still be a poor survey choice if the relevant spectral features are unlikely to reach the S/N required for the measurement. Conversely, AO-driven flux concentration can raise the expected S/N enough to make a weaker source viable.

AO therefore affects the two main quantities that matter to survey planning: spatial resolution and source detectability. This motivates treating AO performance as an explicit input alongside source structure, emission-line flux, redshift, skyline avoidance, and system throughput. Many of these quantities can be estimated for large target samples from existing catalogs and models, but they remain uncertain. That favors a probabilistic rather than deterministic approach. The goal is not simply to assign each target a single estimated S/N value, but

Figure 5: Star maps of the central 0.5° around UltraVISTA-COSMOS (left) and AOFF-A (right). The upper panels show stars from Gaia, with marker size increasing toward brighter stars. The lower panels show selected 2-star (blue) and 3-star (green) asterisms usable with GNAO+GIRMOS within the dashed boxes above. For asterisms that overlap by more than 50%, only the best asterisms are shown to avoid overcrowding the figure. AOFF-A is nearly filled with usable asterisms, whereas COSMOS contains large gaps between them.

Figure 6: Predicted maximum achievable GIRMOS MOAO EE [100 mas] at each sky position across the 1° -wide regions centred on UltraVISTA-COSMOS and AOFF-A.

to estimate the probability that it will exceed the S/N required for a given measurement within an allocated integration time.

The direct route from AO performance to S/N is computationally expensive. It requires an AO-corrected point-spread function (PSF) to be convolved with a source model to determine how much light is delivered to the measurement aperture. This is too slow for survey-scale calculations but can be addressed by chaining ML models. The first ML model infers AO performance metrics from target position within the field and NGS asterism. The second uses those metrics together with simplified source-structure parameters to estimate an effective flux fraction, defined as the fraction of total flux delivered to a particular spatial element. This provides a compact intermediate quantity that can be fed into rapid S/N calculations. This two-stage ML approach can then be applied across entire target catalogs.

To explore the feasibility of the second ML model, a proof-of-concept training set was constructed from tens of thousands of simulated AO-corrected PSFs generated from random NGS asterisms and target positions, together with a corresponding synthetic galaxy catalog. The galaxy catalog was built from physically motivated ranges in morphological parameters to train the model on realistic variation in source size and spatial profile shape. For each AO-corrected PSF-galaxy pair, a model of the galaxy was constructed and convolved with the simulated PSF to compute the effective flux fraction at various spatial locations across the galaxy.

A multi-layer perceptron was then trained on this dataset to directly predict effective flux fraction from the AO performance metrics and source-model parameters. In effect, this second model compresses the expensive PSF-plus-convolution step into an output that can be evaluated rapidly across large target samples. Current results reproduce the simulated values with an accuracy of approximately 20% RMS. This accuracy is not yet sufficient for final survey ranking, and further improvement through continued refinement of the input features and a fuller assessment of the impact of this error will be the subject of future work. It is sufficient, however, to demonstrate that AO performance and source-model parameters can be combined through an ML model in a form fast enough for target-level inference at survey scale.

The predicted effective flux fraction can then be incorporated into a simple vectorized exposure-time calculation. Combined with redshift, skyline, and throughput information, this supports Monte Carlo propagation of uncertainties in quantities such as emission-line flux, redshift, velocity dispersion, and potentially observing conditions. The result is a S/N distribution for each target rather than a single deterministic estimate. Targets can then be selected on the basis of both scientific interest and probability of success. For example, a survey might require that targets satisfy a spatial-resolution criterion and also exceed a threshold such as $P(S/N > 5) > 0.8$ within a fixed exposure time.

This is the most exploratory part of the framework, but also the point at which its survey-design motivation becomes clearest. Probabilistic S/N-based target selection provides a natural way to design AO-aware surveys under uncertainty. It reframes the problem from what can be observed with AO to the probability of obtaining

data with the required S/N to support the science goals. That shift makes it possible to compare different survey strategies on a common statistical footing.

5. OUTLOOK

The framework described here remains under development, and substantial work is still required to refine and validate its individual components. Its direction, however, is already clear. The long-term aim is to support AO-aware survey design by incorporating AO performance from the beginning rather than treating it as a later constraint. An important first use is to apply the framework to compare three distinct approaches to AO-aware survey design on a consistent basis.

One option is to build AO-aware surveys within existing deep fields, where ancillary data are richest and the supporting information available for each target is already strongest. The key question is whether those fields can also deliver the spatial resolution and S/N required by the intended science, although the comparisons in Section 3 already suggest that this may be challenging for most of them. A second option is to develop new fields in regions with high and relatively uniform expected AO performance. Here the question is whether the scientific gains justify the substantial investment needed to build comparable ancillary data, potentially through future wide-area imaging from facilities such as Euclid and the Nancy Grace Roman Space Telescope [30]. A third option is to draw targets from across the accessible sky near especially favorable asterisms, thereby maximizing AO performance while accepting a more limited set of supporting data. These approaches differ in achievable AO performance, efficient use of target catalogs, and the depth and uniformity of ancillary data, making it important to compare them explicitly rather than assume that any one of them is optimal for all science cases.

This work has outlined a single survey-design workflow that connects rapid AO prediction, sky- and field-level performance mapping, and probabilistic target selection. Key next steps are the public release of the AO performance prediction tools described in Section 2, release of the AO-sky maps and related tools described in Section 3, application of the framework to emerging wide-area datasets such as Euclid, and refinement of the probabilistic tools needed to compare AO-aware survey design strategies explicitly.

As AO becomes more important on current large telescopes and future ELT-class facilities, the need for survey-design tools that account for AO from the start will grow. For ELT-class spectroscopic facilities in particular, including HARMONI and MOSAIC [10, 11], that need is likely to increase as AO-assisted observations are applied to larger samples and finer spatial scales. The planned public release is intended to make the AO prediction tools, AO-sky maps, and target-selection methods usable across a wider range of instruments and science cases. By linking deep-field and wide-survey approaches, it is intended both to guide target selection for individual surveys and to support a more explicitly survey-scale approach to AO-driven science.

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